

TEACHER AS A MULTIFACETED PERSONALITY: A NEED OF THE PRESENT TIME

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ABSTRACT

Education in twenty-first-century India has seen a profound transformation. The development in communication technology has affected the very role of a teacher. The earlier goal of “education for all” has now become the pursuit of “quality and purpose-driven education for all.” The teacher is no longer limited to delivering textbook content; instead, teachers are facilitators, guides, researchers, innovators, technologists, and moral exemplars. National policy documents such as the *National Curriculum Framework* (NCERT, 2005), the *National Curriculum Framework for Teacher Education* (NCTE, 2009), and the *National Professional Standards for Teachers* (NCTE, 2022) reinforce this broader vision.

This paper is an attempt to show the need of multifaceted teacher to fulfil the demands of techno Savy generation. The teacher as a multifaceted personality will examine the pedagogical, ethical, social, and technological dimensions of education. Taking insights from the Indian educationists such as J. C. Agrawal, S. S. Chauhan, Kireet Joshi, and Jandhyala Tilak, the paper argues that the identity of the teacher in India must be reconstructed through reflective practice, value-based education, and context-specific innovation to address the needs of a rapidly transforming society.

Key Words: Education, multifaceted, pedagogy, curriculum, learner, facilitator

In India, the teacher has long held a sacred position, deeply rooted in the *Guru–Shishya Parampara* (tradition) that blended intellectual development with moral and spiritual guidance. However, in the contemporary age, the teacher’s role has expanded beyond these traditional boundaries to include technological innovations, new pedagogy, research aptitude, and professional accountability (Agrawal 67). The *National Education Policy 2020* and the *National Professional Standards for Teachers (2022)* describe teachers as the “heart of the learning process” and the “most critical factor in ensuring quality education.” This vision requires teachers to be simultaneously knowledge creators, ethical guides, community leaders, and reflective practitioners. Their professional identity is therefore multifaceted and fluid, means continuously evolving with pedagogical needs, social realities, and moral commitments to the profession.

Teaching in India has always been more than an occupation; it is a vocation guided by philosophy and purpose. The teacher, in this sense, is not merely an employee of an institution but a philosopher who helps learners achieve self-realization (*swadharma* and *atma-vikas*) (Joshi 56). Thinkers such as Swami Vivekananda and Sri Aurobindo viewed education as the “manifestation of the perfection already in man.” Teachers, therefore, were to serve as facilitators who awaken the learner’s inner potential rather than impose external authority. Gurudev Rabindranath Tagore also has same views regarding education. His philosophy of education where nature and freedom plays vital role, he worked out it in the formation of a school *Shanti -Niketan*, a school without ‘walls’ in the abode of nature with plenty of freedom and choices for the students to learn from.

Modern scholars like Kireet Joshi (2013) and R. Dhankar (2018) stress the same idea within a contemporary framework: intellectual training must go hand in hand with moral and emotional development. As Dhankar makes a point, “Education that ignores the ethical and emotional foundations of personality ends up producing incomplete human beings” (42). Hence, the teacher must inculcate virtues such as integrity, compassion, and discipline, serving as an example of ethical behaviour. This moral dimension aligns with the *National Curriculum Framework* (2005), which places “values and life skills” at the centre of educational reform (NCERT 12). The Indian teacher’s multifaceted identity therefore begins with being a moral philosopher, deeply grounded in the nation’s spiritual heritage yet open to global perspectives.

A defining feature of modern teacher education in India is the idea of reflective practice. The *National Curriculum Framework for Teacher Education* (2009) highlights reflection, self-inquiry, and critical awareness as essential aspects of professional identity. According to NCTE, teachers must develop the ability “to look back critically on their practices, beliefs, and assumptions” and refine them in response to evolving educational contexts (NCTE 23). S. S. Chauhan (2016) defines reflection as “*a deliberate process of self-evaluation through which teachers improve their classroom effectiveness and ethical awareness*” (91). Likewise, Singh and Sharma (2004) advocate for integrating reflection into teacher training through action research, and peer learning process.

In India’s diverse socio-cultural environment, reflective practice becomes even more important. Teachers work across various linguistic, cultural, and economic atmosphere. A reflective teacher adapts pedagogy to local needs, whether teaching in a rural school with limited resources or an urban classroom rich in technology (Mukhopadhyay and Parhar 117). This capacity to connect theory with practice defines the professional excellence of Indian educators. The teacher’s role today extends far beyond just delivering lessons. Influenced by the constructivist approach, the teacher now acts as a facilitator who encourages students to construct their own understanding. NCERT (2005) promotes this learner-centred perspective. The facilitator designs meaningful learning experiences, promotes inquiry, and cultivates critical thinking among the students. So that they keep on learning even after completion of their education. As it has been said that learning never comes to an end.

As Agrawal says, “*Learning becomes authentic only when the teacher creates opportunities for learners to explore, question, and connect classroom concepts to real-life situations*” (114). The teacher’s role, therefore, resembles that of a gardener who nurtures growth rather than a mechanic who repairs machines. In India’s multilingual and socio-economically diverse classrooms, facilitation also means bridging gaps—helping first-generation learners, addressing linguistic differences, and linking education with everyday life. NCERT (2005) emphasizes that teachers must “organize learning around meaningful experiences rather than rote content” (48). Hence, facilitative teaching is central to democratizing education and making it inclusive.

Technology has revolutionized education, especially after the COVID-19 pandemic. Teachers today must integrate digital tools, multimedia, and online platforms into their pedagogy (Pillai 83). However, technology should enhance, not replace, the human connection in learning. As Mukhopadhyay (2017) notes, “Technology is a means, not an end—it should empower teachers to personalize learning and foster creativity” (132). Policies like NEP 2020 and NPST 2022 recognize digital literacy as a core professional competency for teachers.

Innovative educators use technology to reach marginalized learners, develop blended learning models, and promote interactive engagement. Initiatives such as SWAYAM, DIKSHA, and

PM e-Vidya demonstrate the Indian government's commitment to teacher-led innovation. In this way, teachers emerge as digital facilitators, researchers, and creative problem-solvers reshaping the learning landscape (Tilak 155). Modern teacher education emphasizes research as an integral part of teaching. Pillai (2014) argues that teachers must develop "a spirit of inquiry and experimentation" to create context-specific knowledge (92). Action research enables teachers to examine classroom challenges, generate insights, and contribute to educational improvement.

The NCTE (2009) framework describes "research-mindedness" as a hallmark of professional teachers, encouraging them to identify problems, analyse outcomes, and share best practices. This culture of inquiry promotes autonomy and supports evidence-based educational reform (Singh and Sharma 76). Moreover, lifelong learning defines the truly multifaceted teacher. Continuous Professional Development (CPD) programs, MOOCs, and initiatives like NISHTHA and DIKSHA empower teachers to update their skills throughout their careers. In a rapidly changing knowledge society, teachers must remain perpetual learners to stay relevant and effective

A teacher in India is expected not only to teach but also to embody ethical values and promote social harmony. Kireet Joshi (2013) insists that "*education should awaken the soul of the learner and connect knowledge with values such as compassion, integrity, and self-control*" (63). R. A. Sharma (2019) similarly emphasizes that teachers must model fairness, respect, and empathy in their conduct. In a pluralistic country like India, teachers act as agents of inclusivity, fostering gender equality, secularism, and intercultural respect (Dhankar 60; Govinda 23).

The *National Curriculum Framework* (2005) reinforces this role by integrating art, heritage, and moral education into the curriculum (NCERT 77). The teacher as a moral and cultural leader thus becomes a cornerstone of ethical nation-building. Throughout history, Indian teachers have contributed to nation-building. From Gandhi's *Nai Talim* to Tagore's *Visva-Bharati*, educators have served as reformers who linked education with social transformation. Contemporary thinkers like Jandhyala Tilak (2018) note that "teachers are the most powerful agents in reducing social and educational inequality" (149).

Modern initiatives like *Samagra Shiksha Abhiyan* and *Beti Bachao Beti Padhao* depend on teachers' engagement with communities. To fulfill this role, teachers must be aware of social realities—gender bias, caste inequality, and poverty—and use education as a tool for empowerment (Mukhopadhyay and Parhar 128). By bridging the gap between schools and society, teachers ensure that education remains a means of liberation rather than exclusion.

CHALLENGES BEFORE THE INDIAN TEACHER:-

While the idea of the multifaceted teacher is inspiring, Indian educators face significant challenges. Overcrowded classrooms, outdated infrastructure, administrative overload, and limited professional autonomy often reduce teaching to mechanical routine (Anand and Sharma 104). Recruitment delays, inadequate training, and declining social status further hinder progress (Varghese and Gupta 2023). The inclusion of IKS (Indian Knowledge Systems) in the curriculum expected the more enthusiastic teachers to learn something new so that they can deal with these papers too.

Teacher shortages are particularly alarming in higher education. For instance, in Madhya Pradesh, 17 universities report that 81% of teaching positions are vacant, with five universities functioning entirely with temporary or guest faculty. Such conditions severely affect quality. Post-COVID, attention spans have shortened, and social media distractions

have multiplied. Permanent teachers are also burdened with excessive non-academic and clerical responsibilities, leaving them little time for reflection or innovation.

Addressing these issues demands systemic reforms like strengthening teacher education, ensuring continuous professional development, and restoring dignity and recognition to the teaching profession (Agrawal 145; NCTE 2022). Despite these hurdles, countless teachers across India, working in both rural and urban settings, continue to embody the spirit of service, creativity, and nation-building.

CONCLUSION

Today's Indian teacher stands at the crossroads of tradition and modernity. The ancient image of the *Guru* has evolved into that of a reflective, innovative, and socially responsible professional. A multifaceted teacher is at once a philosopher, facilitator, researcher, technologist, and moral leader. Such educators are vital for realizing the vision of equitable and quality education outlined in the *National Education Policy 2020*.

As J. C. Agrawal (2019) aptly notes, “*A teacher's worth lies not only in what he knows but in what he inspires others to become*” (167). Teaching, therefore, is not confined to classroom teaching only, now it is a moral and spiritual calling that shapes the destiny of the nation. Preparing multifaceted teachers in India is not simply a policy goal; it is a need of a present time.

REFERENCES

1. Agrawal, J. C. *Teacher and Education in a Developing Society*. 5th ed., Vikas Publishing House, 2019.
2. Anand, C. L., and S. R. Sharma. *Teacher Education and the Emerging Society*. NCERT, 2018.
3. Bhatia, K. K., and J. N. Arora. *The Teacher and Education in Emerging Indian Society*. Tandon Publications, 2015.
4. Chauhan, S. S. *Innovations in Teaching Learning Process*. Vikas Publishing House, 2016.
5. Dhankar, R. *Education in Emerging Indian Society*. Aakar Books, 2018.
6. Govinda, R., editor. *Who Goes to School? Exploring Exclusion in Indian Education*. Oxford University Press, 2011.
7. Joshi, Kireet. *Education for Character Development*. Indian Council of Philosophical Research, 2013.
8. Mukhopadhyay, M., and Madhu Parhar. *Education in Emerging Indian Society: Issues, Challenges and Prospects*. Shipra Publications, 2017.
9. NCERT. *National Curriculum Framework 2005*. NCERT, 2005.
10. NCTE. *National Curriculum Framework for Teacher Education (NCFTE)*. NCTE, 2009.
11. NCTE. *National Professional Standards for Teachers (NPST)*. NCTE, Government of India, 2022.
12. Pillai, K. R. *Teacher Education in India: Quality Concerns and Policy Implications*. Concept Publishing Company, 2014.

13. Sharma, R. A. *Foundations of Education*. Loyal Book Depot, 2019.
Singh, L. C., and K. D. Sharma, editors. *Teacher Education: A Source Book*. NCERT, 2004.
14. Singh, Y. K., and T. Sharma. *Teacher Education: Principles, Theories and Practices*. APH Publishing Corporation, 2018.
15. Tilak, Jandhyala B. G. *Education and Development in India: Critical Issues in Public Policy and Development*. Springer, 2018.
16. Varghese, N. V., and R. Gupta, editors. *India Higher Education Report 2023: Teachers, Teaching and Teacher Education in India*. Routledge, 2023.